

Evaluation of ACS Reweighting Methods in Counties

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Abstract.

The goals and scope of this paper are:

- (a) to describe the underlying data and idea for a new internal evaluation methodology applied to the reweighting of American Community Survey (ACS) single-year data for years 2018–2022;
- (b) to provide theory based on mixed-effect linear models supporting the methodology; and
- (c) to summarize the results of the evaluations made so far using available data.

Models and data exhibits are presented for ACS county-level estimates (for the 2093 counties with 2020 estimated population greater than 15,000), for 47 outcome variables, based on several weighting methods including some making use of administrative records via Inverse Probability Weighting. The models use quadratic regression to describe estimates across data years, and allow for variance components with strong estimated correlations among different weighting-method outcomes, which may have variances combining SDR with county-level AR(1) components across time. Five different models are compared, using a penalized-likelihood approach similar to AIC, first when models are fitted separately for all distinct county and variable pairs, and later when coefficients and variance parameters are shared across county population-size classes. The paper draws preliminary conclusions about weighting-method effectiveness through examination across counties and variables of standardized residuals for 2020 from the fitted models of ACS estimates.

Key words. Small area estimation, studentized residuals, variance components, model comparison.

1. Motivation and Data Structure

Motivated both by ongoing declines in ACS response rates and by COVID-19-related interruptions and deficiencies in ACS data collection for data year 2020, the Census Bureau is considering improved methods of reweighting and calibrating ACS data to achieve valid representation of the target US population. In the past, calibration has been based on demographic and geographic variables for which high-quality yearly totals were provided by the Census Bureau’s Population Estimates Program. However, the patterns of characteristics of the respondent and nonrespondent populations were definitely different in 2020 than in other data-years (Shin et al. 2021; Rothbaum and Bee 2021) in ways that cannot be summarized adequately in terms of those demographic and geographic variables but may be partially captured by economic variables found in administrative records (*ibid.*). For that reason, and to enable longer-term improvements in weighting, administrative records data incorporating economic variables are now being explored in developing new methods of reweighting the 2020 and later ACS data (*ibid.*, Eggleston et al. 2024).

A Census Bureau workgroup is currently exploring techniques for reweighting ACS survey data with several different approaches using administrative records data, base-weight modeling, and calibration techniques.

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These techniques are documented elsewhere in detail (Kang et al. 2022, Rothbaum and Bee 2021, Eggleston et al. 2024). But a necessary task in this research is to provide a principled comparative evaluation of the different reweighting approaches. Such evaluations are hard to come by because there is no alternative, external source of most of the outcome variable totals or proportions that are estimated from the original or reweighted ACS. The present paper provides one such evaluation strategy.

Effective evaluations should consider survey estimates based on different survey-weighting strategies for multiple outcome variables and multiple geographies over multiple data years. The practice in the Census Bureau and other federal statistical agencies is to examine design and analysis changes with respect to temporal stability and geographic and demographic consistency. Here we emphasize the criterion of temporal stability or instability in the anomalous data-year 2020.

In this paper, survey estimates are considered for all counties with 2020 population size 15,000 or greater, for outcome variables that include some person and housing variables that are and some that are not thought to have changed much in the year 2020 from preceding and following years. For example, household income and employment categories might have been expected to change markedly in 2020 due to COVID, especially for specific demographic groups. On the other hand, building type should not have varied much from year to year due to the slow changes in housing stock, considering that the ACS survey is address-based. However, many ACS survey responses even for such stable variables could have been affected by COVID through changed at-home times and response patterns.

The primary data in this problem take the form of a multi-way array Y_{cwt} of survey-weighted county means of specified outcome variables in each data-year. The indices are respectively: $c = 1, \dots, 2093$ for counties with 2020 estimated population sizes 15,000 and above; w labeling 6 alternative re-weighting/calibration strategies that were implemented across all data-years; v for the 47 outcome variables (some at housing-unit and some at person level) for which county-level mean reweighted survey estimates were calculated; and $t = 0, \dots, 4$ indexes data-year 2018, \dots , 2022. Similarly indexed variance estimates V_{cwt} and covariance matrices \mathbf{V}_{cvt} with entries $V_{cvt, w_1 w_2}$ for $w_1, w_2 = 1, \dots, 6$ are available for the county level survey-weighted means. Variances (and more rarely, covariances) are estimated in ACS using formulas involving separately calculated estimates from ACS base-weights multiplied by 80 distinct replicate weight factors, in a procedure called Successive Difference Replication (SDR, Fay & Train 1995). The estimated variances, treated as though known, are used here in some Small-Area-Estimation model-based analyses, and correlations across w based on these SDR-estimated quantities are used in all models. Subsection 1.2 further discusses computational aspects of obtaining or approximating these variances and covariances.

The high-level strategy adopted here is to view the data Y_{cwt} , for each (c, w, v) combination, as a short time series of annual observations for 2018 through 2022. At least for variables v for which a properly survey-weighted estimate should have been fairly stable over the 5 years, the standardized residual of the observation in 2020 versus the prediction within a model based on all 5 years will be used as a diagnostic in deciding which of the reweighting methods w are working well. Our approach, for such variables, is to construct some overall measure of stability – of standardized residuals being well centered or not being too large – aggregated across all counties or within size-classes of counties. By contrast, for variables v whose county-level values *would* be expected to be very different in the COVID year 2020 than in the other years, our residual diagnostic aggregated across counties should show the $t = 2$ year-2020 observation relatively *often* to be an outlier.

1.1 Reductions and Constraints based on Preliminary Data Analysis

Several re-weighting methods were initially chosen for analysis because they were implemented for all data-years. Three different methods of inverse probability weighting (IPW) models were used to predict response on the subset of ACS-sampled units matched to administrative-records data: fitting a single tree (`cart` or recursive partitioning), fitting multiple small trees by gradient boosting (`gbm`), and ordinary logistic regression (`logit`) with many predictive administrative-record (AR) variables but no interactions. For each of the IPW modeling methods, there was also the possibility of raking to AR totals. The 5 IPW methods actually implemented were:

`cart` with AR raking, and `gbm` and `logit` each with or without AR raking

All these methods produced modified base-weights, which were then raked to demographic/geographic totals (Population Estimates) in standard ACS fashion. The methods are compared with the standard ACS production method (`Prod`) for reference.

Unsurprisingly, when final ACS weights were based on the several IPW-model modifications of base-weights, the corresponding survey-weighted estimates of totals or proportions for ACS outcome variables at large- or medium-sized county level were highly correlated. These correlations, across the board for many different outcome variables, were mostly 0.9 and above. Moreover, the weights based on `gbm` and `logit` IPW models were so similar that they produced county survey-weighted totals with correlations 0.97 (usually 0.99) and above. These extremely high correlations applied to totals from AR-raked weights for `gbm` and `logit` and separately to `gbm` and `logit` based weights that were not AR-raked. (The correlations between weighted totals from weights that were raked versus those that were not were still high, but somewhat lower.) Accordingly, we merged the raked `gbm` and `logit` weights, respectively called `gbmlgt.rak` when AR-raked and `gbmlgt.no` otherwise, by averaging the two separate sets of weights. This left 4 distinct weighting methods (indexed $w = 1, \dots, 4$) to be compared:

`cart.rak`, `gbmlgt.rak`, `gbmlgt.no`, `Prod` (*)

Here `Prod` denotes the standard production method of ACS weighting, the most recent methodology for which is documented in US Census Bureau (2022).

1.2 Comparability of Variance Estimates for Different Weighting Schemes

The computational burden involved in generating a national set of ACS adjusted weights differs dramatically between the different IPW and production models. The computer-intensive `gbm` model-fitting has so far made it infeasible to re-run these IPW calculations 81 times at national level based on ACS base-weights multiplied by SDR replicate weight-factors. That would have been the preferred approach to variance calculation for survey-weighted totals based on IPW-method reweighting. Such re-calculation was feasible and was done both for the logistic and for the production weighting methods, but so far not for the `cart` method.

To maintain comparability between survey-total SDR variances calculated for weighted totals based on the four weight-types (*), Jonathan Eggleston computed the SDR-replicate county-level estimates for all outcome variables and re-weighting methods starting from the post-IPW-model ‘base-weights’ (for the IPW-reweighting methods) or from the usual ACS base-weights in the production weighting-method. We used these to compute the variances V_{cwt} and covariances V_{cwt,w_1w_2} mentioned above as part of the basic data-structure. Covariances obtained in this way quantify the sampling variability of survey totals based on final weights when base-weights (IPW-modeled or not) are regarded as fixed in advance. However, this approach does not take account of variability of the administrative records or processing used in IPW modeling.

Our working group has discussed whether the replicate-based variance estimators adequately capture the variability due to the use of AR predictors in an overparameterized Gradient Boosting or Recursive Partitioning (CART) model. For these weighting methods, the answer seems to be ‘no’, and we are exploring how else to estimate the covariances in a principled way. In later sections, this paper considers to what extent model-based variance-component estimates can fill this need.

For the logistic regression IPW method, the SDR-type variances obtained by post-IPW replication can be compared directly with the more detailed but still feasible SDR variances obtained by applying weight-replicates to the original base-weights and performing the logistic-regression models 81 times. Our working group will continue to conduct and analyze those comparisons, as well as a more limited set of comparisons between `gbm` variances done by IPW modeling at single-state level, replicated either on the original ACS base-weights or on the post-`gbm` base-weights.

Variances were compared for outcome variables tabulated at the level of counties of population 15,000 and above. In these comparisons, the variances of the survey estimates obtained with production weights are very similar to variances from the IPW weighting methods, whether or not they calibrated to administrative-records totals, when the SDR estimates were based on post-IPW outputs as though the weights including modeled IPW propensities were base-weights. Moreover, the variances of survey estimates for logistic-regression IPW models fully replicated from the actual design base-weights are again much the same. This is puzzling, since one might expect stochastic aspects (such as missing items or absent units from some administrative files) in the ARs used in logistic regression to contribute a level of variability beyond the post-IPW SDR.

2. Modeling Ideas

The main idea in the present paper is to analyze for each (v, w) the collection across $c = 1, \dots, 2093$ of standardized residuals for the $t = 2$ (data-year 2020) observation.

In this Section, we initially describe models for data Y_{cwt} considered separate and independent for each (c, v) combination as a data vector with 20-dimensional components (t, w) . We provide a small hierarchy of partially nested models with parameter dimension ranging from 3 to 6, treating SDR estimated variance-covariances across w as though they are known. Next we provide some data-analytic AIC-based comparisons between the various models fitted, across (c, v) combinations, and describe and interpret also the aggregated log-likelihoods across size-classes of counties. Somewhat surprisingly, this aggregation often does not suggest the models with most detailed parameterization including SDR variances as the most successful.

2.1 Models for individual (c, v)

The models under consideration all build on the same quadratic regression with respect to time, and within each model, the regression coefficients do not vary with weighting-method w , because all methods attempt to estimate the same (c, v, t) county mean for the specified variable and data-year. The models for Y_{cwt} have fixed effects that are quadratic in t and one or two independent variance components u_{cwt} and e_{cwt} each of which is mean-0 and jointly normal. The component e models pure sampling-errors. while unmodeled (c, v) -specific random errors in the quadratic signal are incorporated in variance-component u with AR(1) structure over time and with a known correlation structure \mathbf{C}_{cv} with respect to w as given in (1).

In all models, the SDR-estimated covariances for methods w among Y_{cwt} are combined for fixed (c, v) by

averaging across t , according to the definition

$$\bar{V}_{cv,w_1w_2} = \frac{1}{5} \sum_{t=1}^5 V_{cvt,w_1w_2} \quad , \quad \bar{C}_{cv,w_1w_2} = \frac{\bar{V}_{cv,w_1w_2}}{\bar{V}_{cv,w_1w_1}^{1/2} \bar{V}_{cv,w_2w_2}^{1/2}} \quad (1)$$

and by treating $\bar{C}_{cv} \equiv \bar{C}_{cv,w_1w_2}$ as though it is known.

The general form of the models for fixed (c, v) is Generalized Linear with normal errors for data $y_{t,w} \equiv Y_{cvt}$ viewed as a 20-dimensional vector \underline{y} indexed by (t, w) in lexicographical order (with t -index moving faster). The design matrix \mathbf{X} is 20×3 consisting of 4 stacked copies of identical 5×3 design matrices \mathbf{X}_0 equal to the bound columns $\{\underline{1}, \mathbf{0} : 4, (\mathbf{0} : 4)^2\}$. The models are given by

$$\underline{y} = \mathbf{X}\beta + \underline{\epsilon} \equiv \mathbf{X}\beta + \underline{e} + \underline{u} + \underline{\epsilon}^o \quad , \quad \underline{\epsilon} \sim \mathcal{N}_{20}(\underline{0}, \Sigma) \quad (2)$$

where $\beta = (a, b, q)$ below, and the 20×20 patterned variance matrices

$$\Sigma = \alpha \mathbf{V}^{(c,v)} + \Sigma^u + \lambda_0 \mathbf{I}_{20 \times 20} \quad (3)$$

for fixed (c, v) arise as the superposed variances of independent errors

$$\underline{e} \sim \mathcal{N}(\underline{0}, V^{(c,v)}) \quad , \quad \underline{u} \sim \mathcal{N}(\underline{0}, \Sigma^u) \quad , \quad \underline{\epsilon}^o \sim \mathcal{N}(\underline{0}, \lambda_0 \mathbf{I}_{20 \times 20})$$

Here $V^{(c,v)}$ and Σ^u have entries

$$V_{(t_1,w_1),(t_2,w_2)}^{(c,v)} = \delta_{t_1,t_2} V_{cvt_1,w_1,w_2} \quad , \quad \Sigma_{(t_1,w_1),(t_2,w_2)}^u = \sigma_{cvw_1} \sigma_{cvw_2} \bar{C}_{cv,w_1,w_2} \cdot \rho_{cv}^{|t_1-t_2|} \quad (4)$$

The indicator $\alpha \in \{0, 1\}$ of the variance-component $\mathbf{V}^{(c,v)}$ is treated as known, and $\lambda > 0$ is a fixed (known) small number used solely to avoid matrix ill-conditioning. Models with $\alpha = 1$ include the estimated SDR covariances within Σ , and models with $\sigma = 0$ or $\rho \equiv 0$ have no other time-correlation, while \underline{u} in models with $\sigma^2 > 0$ and ρ estimated has AR(1) temporal structure.

Variance parameters $V^{(c,v)}$ when estimated directly from SDR continue to depend on c, v and also on w but not on t . In those AR(1) models that allow time dependence between estimates with common (c, v) , the correlation ρ_{cv} does not depend on w . In all models with Σ^u variance components, variances σ_{cvw}^2 are allowed to depend on w , but preliminary data analysis always found the variances among the IPW weighting methods ($w = 1, 2, 3$) to be so similar that σ_{cvw}^2 values are taken to be identical and unknown for these w 's, with a second unknown variance parameter σ_{cv4}^2 for the Prod weighting method.

A listing of the resulting models to be fitted is **(M1)**-**(M5)** as follows. The data-vectors \underline{y} and error-vectors $\underline{e}, \underline{u}, \underline{\epsilon}^o$ are all indexed by (t, w) for fixed (c, v) , with variance matrices as given in (4).

- (M1)** Quadratic regression $y_{tw} = Y_{cvt} = a_{cv} + b_{cv} \cdot t + q_{cv} \cdot t^2 + e_{tw} + \underline{\epsilon}_{tw}^o$, where $\underline{e} \sim \mathcal{N}(\underline{0}, V^{(c,v)})$
- (M2)** $y_{tw} = a_{cv} + b_{cv} \cdot t + q_{cv} \cdot t^2 + u_{tw} + \underline{\epsilon}_{tw}^o$, where $\underline{u} \sim \mathcal{N}(\underline{0}, \Sigma^u)$ with $\sigma_{cv1}^2, \sigma_{cv4}^2$ but $\rho \equiv 0$
- (M3)** $y_{tw} = a_{cv} + b_{cv} \cdot t + q_{cv} \cdot t^2 + u_{tw} + \underline{\epsilon}_{tw}^o$, where $\underline{u} \sim \mathcal{N}(\underline{0}, \Sigma^u)$ with general ρ_{cv}
- (M4)** $y_{tw} = a_{cv} + b_{cv} \cdot t + q_{cv} \cdot t^2 + e_{tw} + u_{tw} + \underline{\epsilon}_{tw}^o$, where $\underline{u} \sim \mathcal{N}(\underline{0}, \Sigma^u)$ with $\rho \equiv 0$
- (M5)** $y_{tw} = a_{cv} + b_{cv} \cdot t + q_{cv} \cdot t^2 + e_{tw} + u_{tw} + \underline{\epsilon}_{tw}^o$, where $\underline{e} \sim \mathcal{N}(\underline{0}, V^{(c,v)})$ and $\underline{u} \sim \mathcal{N}(\underline{0}, \Sigma^u)$ with general ρ_{cvw}

Table 1: Parameter dimension for each (size 20) (t, w) dataset for each (c, v) combination, under each of the models being considered. Variances $V^{(c,v)}$ and covariances \bar{C} are treated as known.

Model	$\dim(\beta)$	$\dim(\sigma)$	$\dim(\rho)$	Total Dim
M1	3	0	0	3
M2	3	2	0	5
M3	3	2	1	6
M4	3	2	0	5
M5	3	2	1	6

Thus, in models (M2)–(M3), $\alpha = 0$ in (4) and the $V^{(c,v)}$ variance component is absent, while in models (M4)–(M5), $\alpha = 1$ and the $V^{(c,v)}$ variance component is present. Models (M2) and (M4) allow only the unknown variance parameters $\sigma_{cv1}^2, \sigma_{cv4}^2$ in Σ^u , while models (M3) and (M5) allow ρ_{cv} as well. Since we treat the SDR-based variances $V^{(c,v)}$ as known in models (M1), (M4) and (M5), with \bar{C} treated as known in all models, the dimension of the unknown parameters for the models for each (c, v) is given in Table 1.

2.2 Model Comparisons

Models (M1)–(M5) were fitted to all of the (c, v) ACS data Y_{cwt} described above. For all fitted models, the ridge-parameter λ_0 in (4) used to enforce well-conditioned invertible variance matrices was $\lambda_0 = 10^{-6}$. A few (2900, a rounded number) of the 2093×47 combinations (c, v) were excluded from model fitting because of too few nonzero data values or because the SDR variance estimates were 0.

In an effort to understand which model features were necessary to successful model fitting, we found for each (c, v) the best model according to the modified Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) by minimizing the penalized quantity $-2 \cdot \log\text{Lik}(Y^{cv}; \hat{\theta}) + 2 \cdot \dim(\theta)$ across the 5 models, where θ denotes the unknown parameter components $(a, b, q, \sigma_1^2, \sigma_4^2, \rho)$ plus any parameters considered to be part of the estimated SDR variances appearing in each model. We did this in two different ways, once treating the SDR variance-covariance parameter estimates as ‘known’ – costing 0 in the $\dim(\theta)$ parameter-count, and once with the parameter dimension of 4 accounting for one variance estimated for each weighting-method w . (Thus the overall parameter dimension is as given in the final column of Table 1 when there are 0 SDR-parameters, and when there are 4 SDR ‘parameters’, the (M1)–(M5) overall parameter-dimensions are (7, 5, 6, 9, 10). The counts of (c, v) combination resulting in each of the 5 models as ‘best’ are given in Table 2.

Table 2 suggests that when the ‘cost’ of SDR variance-estimation is taken into account, in the majority of (c, v) cases the Σ^u variance component in (2)–(4) does an adequate job of parameterizing the variance. This conclusion was checked using two different cross-tabulations of the best model chosen (when SDR parameters are deemed to have dimension 4): first across variables v and next by grouping counties into size classes. Best-model counts were tallied by variable, obtaining for each v the counts and proportions of best models across counties. For all v , Models (M1) and (M3) were most frequently and (M4)–(M5) least frequently the best, but there were some notable v -specific differences in the distribution of best models among (M1)–(M3). We concluded from this examination (and confirmed) that maximized loglikelihood differences among models (M1)–(M3) were often small, reflecting the noisiness of model fitting with data vectors of dimension 20.

The cross-tabulation of best-model proportions over all variables when counties were subdivided by size-classes was more illuminating. For this purpose, 13 size-classes containing similar numbers of counties

Table 2: Rounded counts of best models under two different AIC calculations.

SDR ‘parameter’	Models found best by AIC					Total*
Dim	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	All
0	66,500	4,500	20,500	1,200	3,100	95,500
4	37,500	15,000	42,000	200	600	95,500

* Total numbers exclude 2900 data-poor (c, v) combinations.

Table 3: Numbers of counties in 13 size-ranges (by 2020 estimated population size, in thousands), among the 2093 counties with population $> 15,000$.

Size-class	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
Min. pop.	15	18.5	22	27	32	40	48	60	80	110	160	250	500
Max. pop.	18.5	22	27	32	40	48	60	80	110	160	250	500	∞
# Cty’s	194	181	194	142	197	164	149	165	152	135	143	137	140

were created, as indicated in Table 3. (M1), (M3), (M2) and (collapsed) (M4)–(M5) were the best models in decreasing proportion in all size-classes. Moreover, there was a clear trend that the larger the size-class, the more often were (M2) and (M3) the best models: the respective proportions in class 1 were 0.66, 0.07, 0.26, 0.01, and in class 13 they were 0.23, 0.17, 0.53, 0.06.

There is another way to see which models were most effective in capturing data patterns at (c, v) level within broad groupings of variables and counties. Deviances $(= -2 \cdot \log \text{Lik})$ for each model-type can be summed across (c, v) for all v and for counties c within county size-classes before comparing them to assess the best fit. These aggregated deviances, rounded to 4 significant figures and divided by 1000, are displayed in the body of Table 4. The best-model assessment for the size-classes, in the spirit of AIC as in Table 2, is performed by penalizing these summed Deviances by the product of 2 times the parameter dimension times the number of non-excluded (c, v) combinations contained in each county size-class. The parameter counts for models (as in the second row of Table 2) are given in the final row of Table 4, and the size-class numbers of combinations are given in the third column. The calculation that minimizes in each row the Deviance plus 2 times the number of combinations times the number of model parameters divided by 1,000 gives the AIC-best model in each size-class, and the table entry in that row and column is displayed in bold-face.

The results, summarized in Table 4, are clear. In the 3 smallest-population size classes, model (M1) is best, while in the 8 largest population-size classes (M3) is best. If the parameter dimension for SDR estimates appearing in models (M1), (M4) and (M5) were deemed as large as 6, then model (M3) would have been best in all size-classes. A rough conclusion is that the model without SDR variance component $V^{(c,v)}$ and with SE and correlation parameter $\sigma_{cv1}, \sigma_{cv4}, \rho_{cv}$ does an adequate job at the (c, v) model level of summarizing errors in the quadratic regression model (2).

We examine next the Model (M3) fitted SE and correlation parameters $(\sigma_{cv1}, \sigma_{cv4}, \rho_{cv})$ across the (c, v) combinations. The SE parameters can be compared first of all to the SDR-based SEs averaged across data years, respectively for IPW weighting methods $w = 1, 2, 3$ and for the Prod weighting method $w = 4$. The main idea in doing this is to see whether the model-fitted parameters suggest differences between IPW-method and Prod-method variances which do not appear directly in the SDR-based SEs.

Table 4: Deviances for fitted (c, v) models for model-types (M1)–(M5) summed over (c, v) within the county size-classes of Table 3 rounded to 4 significant figures and divided by 1,000. Population size-ranges given in thousands. 3rd column gives Ncomb, the rounded count of (c, v) combinations in each size-class, and parameter dimension d per (c, v) combination is given in final row. Deviance/1000 corresponding to smallest AIC (equal to Deviance + 2 · Ncomb · d) is displayed in boldface.

Class	Size-range	Ncomb	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5
1	(15, 18.5]	8,500	-1,595	-1,509	-1,545	-1,601	-1,603
2	(18.5, 22]	8,000	-1,496	-1,416	-1,450	-1,501	-1,503
3	(22, 27]	8,700	-1,659	-1,586	-1,623	-1,677	-1,680
4	(27, 32]	6,400	-1,209	-1,195	-1,222	-1,253	-1,255
5	(32, 40]	9,000	-1,794	-1,755	-1,793	-1,831	-1,834
6	(40, 48]	7,500	-1,521	-1,488	-1,519	-1,546	-1,549
7	(48, 60]	6,900	-1,412	-1,371	-1,400	-1,422	-1,425
8	(60, 80]	7,600	-1,597	-1,567	-1,599	-1,610	-1,613
9	(80, 110]	7,000	-1,497	-1,471	-1,500	-1,507	-1,511
10	(110, 160]	6,300	-1,362	-1,352	-1,378	-1,375	-1,379
11	(160, 250]	6,700	-1,456	-1,452	-1,481	-1,475	-1,481
12	(250, 500]	6,400	-1,433	-1,451	-1,478	-1,464	-1,472
13	(500, ∞]	6,500	-1,420	-1,538	-1,569	-1,542	-1,560
Parameter dimension d			7	5	6	9	10

The model-fitted SE parameters are found to be roughly comparable to the SDR values across the different counties and also across different variables, despite the fact that the v -specific estimates Y_{cvt} , reflect widely different outcome-variable proportions. The 9 variables with the largest median SEs have SE estimates ranging from 0.025 to 0.035, while 22 variables have median SE estimate < 0.01 . Among the SDR SEs, the IPW-method SEs (averaged across the three IPW methods and data-years) tend to be very slightly larger (from 0 to 3 or 4 percent) than the Prod SEs. Section 1.2 already questioned whether the IPW-method SEs adequately account for the variability of coverage of the administrative-record data used in the IPW-weight adjustment. With the Model (M3) estimates, the IPW SE parameter σ_{cv1} tends often to be larger than the Prod SE parameter σ_{cv4} . Figure 1 presents four scatterplots of the median SEs by variable and size-class for the SDR SEs and the Model (M3) parameter estimates. This picture shows (in the lower right panel) that in Models (M3), the IPW SEs are typically larger by 12% than the Prod SEs.

The SDR SEs for IPW-method weighting and Prod weighting (lower left) track remarkably closely along a 45° line. But the Model (M3) SEs for IPW weighting (upper left) are generally slightly smaller than the SDR SEs, while the Model (M3) SEs for Prod weighting (upper right) are considerably smaller than the corresponding SDR SEs. Recall that the model adjusts the mean estimates to vary as smoothly as possible across data year and weighting method but otherwise allows residual values rather than SDR estimates to determine SEs. Therefore the plots can be interpreted to suggest that the IPW method SEs are systematically larger (by at least 12%) than the Prod method SEs after accounting for mean adjustments. Since it seems likely from results presented in Section 2.3 below that the Prod estimates are less well centered than the IPW method estimates, we have an even stronger conclusion that the IPW methods are more variable (for county level estimates) than the Prod method estimates.

Figure 1: Scatterplots comparing SDR and Model (M3) SEs for IPW and for Prod weighting methods. Each point in each plot is the pair of median estimated σ_{cv1} or σ_{cv4} parameters for Model (M3) or the SDR SEs for (the average of the 3) IPW methods or the Prod weighting method, over counties c within size-classes defined in Table 3. Blue lines in all plots have slope 1.

This subsection concludes by examining the Model (M3) fitted ρ_{cv} parameters. Very strikingly, these correlations are mostly either close to -1 or 1 . As one indication of this behavior, consider the proportion of $|\rho_{cv}| < 0.8$ over (c, v) combinations with county c in size-class C_j . As j ranges from 1 to 13, this proportion ranges (not quite monotonically) from 0.019 when $j = 1$ to 0.026 when $j = 13$. The analogous proportion of $|\rho_{cv}| < 0.8$ over all counties c for fixed variable v behaves similarly, ranging between 0.012 for $v = 40$ (`family_hh`) to 0.032 for $v = 8$ (`any_public-assistance`). About 73% of the fitted ρ 's are positive.

2.3 Models Sharing Parameters within County Size-Classes

Our goal is to use fitted models to compare residuals for 2020 county-level variable estimates across weighting methods and summarize the results over (c, v) combinations. Preliminary attempts at doing this found that model predictions and standardized residuals are very noisy and erratic across counties within fixed variables when the modeling is done at individual (c, v) level. For that reason, consider models of similar type to (M1)-(M5) above, but where the unknown parameters are shared across counties c falling in the 13 county size-classes of Table 3.

Small Area Estimation (SAE) literature (Rao and Molina 2015) offers ideas on how to share parameters across different domains in order to *borrow strength* from model predictions. A key idea is to allow un-modeled differences between domains to be expressed through independent domain-level random effects. That is the role played by Σ^u in Models (M2)-(M5). But in standard area-level Small Area Estimation models like the Fay-Herriot model, sampling error is also assumed to be known, although in practice it is estimated, sometimes with additional smoothing by so-called Generalized Variance Functions (GVFs). (See Bell 1999 for discussion of the impact in SAE of variability in estimation of sampling variances, and Wolter 2007 for discussion of GVFs.) Variances assumed known also enter our models (M4)-(M5) through SDR-estimated variance-covariance terms $V^{(c,v)}$.

In our setting, there are no county-level predictive covariates to use in predicting county differences that can be applied to all 47 person- and household-variables, but the 5-data-year time trends can be used in this way. Small Area literature does definitely allow time-series area-level random effects, for example in the paper of Rao and Yu (1994), but in the present context the time series are very short for each (c, w, v) combination and provide little redundancy for estimation of time-trend within area together with AR(1) correlations.

One modeling choice would have been to fit a single model (one of (M1)-(M5)) with parameters the same for all counties c . But preliminary analysis showed that there were noticeably different residual patterns for small and large counties, so instead we fitted what amounts to different, decoupled models for each v and each of the 13 county size-classes in Table 3. We had also tried models in which the parameters $\sigma_{cuv}^2, \rho_{cv}$ depend on c only through its size-class while the quadratic regression parameters $\beta^{(cv)} = (a_{cv}, b_{cv}, q_{cv})$ are distinct for each (c, v) . But with those models too, the fitted $\hat{\beta}^{(cv)}$ parameters were somewhat erratic across individual counties but did follow broad patterns over size classes. So we proceed with the models where all parameters are fitted for combinations (c, v) with c 's grouped into the 13 size-classes of Table 3.

Our first task is to compare the fit of size-class models (M1)-(M5). Now the data for a size-class C_j , $j = 1, \dots, 13$, is $(Y_{cwt} : c \in C_j, w = 1, \dots, 4, t = 0, \dots, 4)$, and the parameter dimensions for the models are the same as in Table 1. The Deviances for the different models, fitted separately for all size-classes C_j and variables v and summed over v for ease of presentation, are given in Table 5 rounded to 4 significant figures and divided by 1,000. In order to compare the fit of these models in the spirit of AIC, we must penalize the Deviance by 2 times the number of fitted parameters for the model. Now we assign a parameter

Table 5: Deviances for fitted size-class-by-variable combination (C_j, v) models for model-types (M2)–(M5) summed over v , rounded to 4 significant figures and divided by 1,000. 3rd column gives Ncomb, the number of non-excluded (c, v) combinations for each size-class. Non-SDR parameter dimension p , along with SDR parameter dimension q per (c, v) combination for $c \in C_j$, are given in final rows. Deviance/1000 corresponding to smallest AIC (equal to Deviance $+2 \cdot \{p + \text{Ncomb} \cdot q\}$) is displayed in boldface.

Class	Size-range	Ncomb	M2	M3	M4	M5
1	(15, 18.5]	8,500	-1,543	-1,563	-1,775	-1,775
2	(18.5, 22]	8,000	-1,454	-1,473	-1,664	-1,663
3	(22, 27]	8,700	-1,586	-1,606	-1,807	-1,804
4	(27, 32]	6,400	-1,185	-1,201	-1,336	-1,337
5	(32, 40]	9,000	-1,722	-1,742	-1,912	-1,905
6	(40, 48]	7,500	-1,443	-1,459	-1,597	-1,594
7	(48, 60]	6,900	-1,331	-1,347	-1,459	-1,456
8	(60, 80]	7,600	-1,519	-1,536	-1,638	-1,641
9	(80, 110]	7,000	-1,425	-1,442	-1,530	-1,533
10	(110, 160]	6,300	-1,305	-1,322	-1,385	-1,383
11	(160, 250]	6,700	-1,406	-1,425	-1,482	-1,486
12	(250, 500]	6,400	-1,407	-1,421	-1,467	-1,473
13	(500, ∞]	6,500	-1,494	-1,515	-1,534	-1,553
Non-SDR param. dimension p			5	6	5	6
SDR param. dimension q			0	0	6	6

dimension of 6 (larger than the 4 used in the second row of Table 2) to the SDR-based SE estimates fitted at the level of individual (c, v) combinations in Models (M4)–(M5); but now the non-SDR parameter dimension for each size-class C_j is the same as the final column of Table 1.

The conclusion from Table 5 is somewhat puzzling: with SDR parameter dimension 6, models (M3)–(M5) turn out ‘best’ in different size-classes. If the SDR parameter dimension q were taken to be 4, then models (M4)–(M5) would be best in all size-classes except the largest-population class. Since SDR variances are estimated separately from the data for all 4 weighting methods and 5 data years, the most reasonable value for q is probably larger than 6. Although AIC comparison with $q \geq 6$ suggests to use Model (M5) in further analyses, many of the $13 \cdot 47$ values of each of the estimated σ_w^2 parameters for $w = 1, 4$ turn out to be close to 0. That is, more than 70% of the fitted σ^2 parameters in the size-class-by-variable models are < 0.0005 . Therefore, to compare SEs it makes more sense to use model (M3), for which $\sigma_{C_j,1} > \sigma_{C_j,4}$ for most size-class and variable combinations in Figure 2. It is puzzling that models (M4) or (M5) with SDR estimated variances often seem not to require an additional variance component, so that the overall variance Σ is essentially the same as $V^{(cv)}$, which is fairly erratic from one (c, v) to another. In evaluating different weighting methods comparatively in terms of standardized residuals in the next Section, it helps to have stably estimated variances. Thus our further analyses are done with model (M3). As we have just seen, the pattern of $\sigma_{C_j,1}$ somewhat larger than $\sigma_{C_j,4}$ SEs persists with the county size-class by variable models as in the individual (c, v) models. Correlations also remained very close to ± 1 in the size-class models: only 11 out of $13 \cdot 47$ size-class ρ values had absolute correlations < 0.95 , and those were also not small, and of the large correlations, 13% were positive. This indicates that the fitted quadratics for the size-class model (M3) tend to weave between the actual Y_{cwt} data across the five times t from 0 to 4.

Figure 2: Scatterplot of SD4 versus SD1 estimates (*cf.* lower-right panel of Fig. 1) under Size-Class by Variable Model (M3). Each point is the pair of estimated $\sigma_{C_j, v1}, \sigma_{C_j, v4}$ parameters, where C_j for $j = 1, \dots, 13$ denote the county size-classes defined in Table 3. Blue line has slope 1.

Plot of SD4 (Prod) vs. SD1 (IPW) Estimates, Model (M3)

3. Standardized Residuals under Size-Class Model (M3)

In this Section, restrict attention exclusively to the (M3) form of the generalized linear model (2)–(4) in which the six $\beta, \sigma_1, \sigma_4, \rho$ parameters are fitted once for each entire data set (Y_{cwtv} , $c \in C_j$, $w = 1, \dots, 4$, $t = 0, \dots, 4$) for a fixed variable v and county size-class C_j . The deviance ($= -2 \cdot \log\text{Lik}$) for such a dataset, written in terms of data 20-vectors $Y^{(c,v)}$ indexed by (t, w) , is

$$\text{Dev}_{j,v} = \sum_{c \in C_j} \left\{ \log(\det(\Sigma^{(c,v)})) + (Y^{(c,v)} - X\beta^{(c,v)})' (\Sigma^{(c,v)})^{-1} (Y^{(c,v)} - X\beta^{(c,v)}) \right\} \quad (5)$$

where (j, v) identifies the size-class and variable combination, and $\beta^{(j,v)}, \sigma_{jv,1}, \sigma_{jv,4}, \rho_{jv}$ the unknown parameters (with j replacing c in the previous notations of equation (4)), and for all $c \in C_j$,

$$\Sigma^{(c,v)} = \Sigma^{u,(c,v)} + \lambda_0 I_{20 \times 20} \quad , \quad \Sigma_{(t_1, w_1), (t_2, w_2)}^u = \sigma_{jvw_1} \sigma_{jvw_2} \bar{C}_{cv, w_1, w_2} \cdot \rho_{jv}^{|t_1 - t_2|}$$

and $\sigma_{jvw_1} = \sigma_{jvw_2} = \sigma_{jvw_3}$ by definition. Parameter estimates are obtained by minimizing $\text{Dev}_{j,v}$, and in particular $\hat{\beta}^{(j,v)}$ satisfies

$$\beta^{(j,v)} = (A^{(j,v)})^{-1} X' \sum_{c \in C_j} (\Sigma^{(c,v)})^{-1} Y^{(c,v)} \quad , \quad A^{(j,v)} = X' \sum_{c \in C_j} (\Sigma^{(c,v)})^{-1} X \quad (6)$$

After estimating 6-dimensional parameters $\theta = (\beta, \sigma, \rho)$ separately for each (j, v) combination, we calculate the residual for $t = 2$ (the year 2020) for each weighting-method w , which is $Y_{tw}^{(c,v)} - (\mathbf{X}_0)_{tw} \hat{\beta}^{(2,v)}$. We also calculate a measure of the standard error of that residual assuming the validity of the model. Under that assumption, if the variance parameters and therefore $\Sigma^{(c,v)}$ were known for each $c \in C_j$, equation (6) implies that the residual takes the form

$$\mathbf{res}_{2,w}^{(c,v)} \equiv Y_{2,w}^{(c,v)} - (1, 2, 4) (A^{(j,v)})^{-1} X' \sum_{c \in C_j} (\Sigma^{(j,v)})^{-1} Y^{(j,v)}$$

Treating $\Sigma^{(c,v)}$ as known for each $c \in C_j$ equal to its Maximum Likelihood estimate for the (j, v) data, we note that the residual is a linear function of the observation vector $Y^{(c,v)}$ and has standard error given by the formula

$$\text{SE}_{\mathbf{res}}^{(c,v)} \approx \left[\Sigma_{(2,w), (2,w)}^{(c,v)} - (1, 2, 4) (A^{(j,v)})^{-1} (1, 2, 4)' \right]^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

This SE formula is used in what follows in approximately standardizing the residual $\mathbf{res}_{2,w}^{(c,v)}$ for $c \in C_j$. Any attempt to account theoretically in this standardization for the variability of variance estimation would necessarily rely heavily on the normal distributional assumption in linear model (M3). That (unjustified) assumption makes such a complicated approach less attractive, so we stick with the approximation in (7).

4. Evaluation of Reweighted ACS Estimates based on Residuals

The goal of this paper has been to create a computational procedure in terms of which the comparative performance of the weighting methods $w = 1, \dots, 4$ can be assessed for county-level estimates of totals or proportions of a variety of ACS outcome variables. The development of the previous sections provides an array of approximately standardized residuals based on the size-class by variable (M3) models, indexed by (c, v, w) :

$$\mathbf{res}_{2,w}^{(c,v)} / \text{SE}_{\mathbf{res}}^{(c,v)} \quad , \quad w = 1, \dots, 4, \quad v = 1, \dots, 47, \quad c \in C_j, \quad j = 1, \dots, 13 \quad (8)$$

How should these be used, to detect systematic failures of one weighting method with respect to others? Our approach to that goal is to scrutinize distributions of the standardized 2020 residuals across counties. However, the behavior of the residuals can be quite different for different outcome variables and for different size-classes of counties, so a detailed examination of weighting-method differences should take account of (C_j, v) differences. Examination of 2020 standardized residuals for many variables suggests some variables can be grouped according to whether the median residuals are systematically positive or systematically negative, within county size-classes or predominantly across all size-classes, for all weighting methods. Only a few variables have small-magnitude median standardized residuals across all size-classes (`citizen` and `disabled` being examples). However, many variables have notably mixed signs with positive medians in classes at one extreme of population size and negative medians at the other. Some of this variety can be seen in the plotted median standardized residuals by size-class for selected variables in Figures 3–5.

Typically, the quantiles of standardized residual distributions out in the tails (the quartiles or the 1st and 9th deciles) tend to line up much better across size-classes for the four weighting methods than do the medians. For that reason, the Figures which are the only exhibits shown here regarding standardized residuals relate to medians within size-classes by variable.

In data analyses done so far, the `Prod` weighting method has standardized residuals somewhat more spread out and much less centered near 0 than the IPW weighting methods. For many variables, median standardized residuals for the three IPW methods line up well with each other, far from 0 and from `Prod`. For other variables, `Prod` and `gbmlgt.no` line up reasonably well systematically across county size-classes but differ from the raked IPW methods `cart.rak` and `gbmlgt.rak` (which are similar to each other). The variety of behaviors, some of which can be seen in Figures 3–5, says that the comparative success of the different IPW weighting methods depends strongly on the size of the county and the specific outcome variable considered.

Tentative conclusions from these analyses are that there are no clear winners among the four weighting methods, largely because there is no external data validating what the county-level estimates should have looked like, although `Prod` appears to be a clear loser. The variety of behaviors seen for the different weighting methods suggests that county-level estimates from `Prod` are fairly far out of line for many ACS outcome variables – because of 2020 data-collection deficiencies coupled with real on-the-ground changes in the population that should have been reflected in the data collected – and that any of the IPW weighting methods make productive use of the administrative records to improve those estimates. However, the variety of behaviors of the size-class medians for selected variables in Figures 3–5 calls out for some further explanation and for a decision rule for when to prefer one IPW weighting method over others. Perhaps further analysis of outcome variables on smaller geographic domains will shed further light on those questions.

Further research is also needed to clarify variable-specific differences between the administrative-records universe and the ACS target population and to illuminate variance estimation for IPW weighting-method estimates. At the same time, it would be very valuable to have some external guidance as to which variables should have been ‘stable’ and should therefore have had very well-centered residuals in year 2020, and which variables were truly shifted in 2020 and should have had their residuals demonstrably off-center with a good weighting method. Methodological improvements in variance estimation and sorting of outcome variables into stable and unstable classes could enable the standardized-residual methodology developed in this paper to do a better job of discriminating systematically among IPW weighting methods.

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Figure 3: Plots of Median Standardized Residuals for selected outcome variables, for 4 weighting methods (`cart.rak` blue, `gbmlgt.no` orange, `gbmlgt.rak` cyan, `Prod` black). Medians taken across all Counties within each of 13 size-classes. Residuals obtained from Size-Class Model (M3). Outcome variables are respectively: proportions of persons in poverty, with any health insurance, with any private health insurance, or with any private health insurance.

Figure 4: Plots of Median Standardized Residuals for selected outcome variables, for 4 weighting methods (`cart.rak` blue, `gbmlgt.no` orange, `gbmlgt.rak` cyan, `Prod` black). Medians taken across all Counties within each of 13 size-classes. Residuals obtained from Size-Class Model (M3). Outcome variables are respectively: proportions of persons in the labor force, and of households with children under 18, mobile homes, or single-family detached homes.

Figure 5: Plots of Median Standardized Residuals for selected outcome variables, for 4 weighting methods (`cart.rak` blue, `gbmlgt.no` orange, `gbmlgt.rak` cyan, `Prod` black). Medians taken across all Counties within each of 13 size-classes. Residuals obtained from Size-Class Model (M3). Outcome variables are respectively: proportions of persons with 4-year college degrees, who do not speak English well, and of family and married households.

